

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Human Reference Atlas Digital Object Release Process

How digital objects are collected, validated, and incorporated into the Human Reference Atlas

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Introduction

The Human Reference Atlas uses more than 10 different types of digital objects to describe and index data in a spatially explicit and semantically consistent way (Börner et al. 2025). Six of these digital objects are developed by human experts, including a) 2-dimensional illustrations of functional tissue units (2D FTUs), b) 3-dimensional representations of organs (3D reference objects), c) tables that name and interlink major anatomical structures, cell types, and biomarkers (ASCT+B tables), d) crosswalk tables that unify cell type labels used by different cell type annotation tools (cell type annotation crosswalks), e) files that define and improve spatial registration of tissue blocks within an organ (millitomes), and f) comprehensive panels of curated antibodies that identify the major anatomical structures and cell types in a specific organ (OMAPs).

This standard operating procedure (SOP) focuses on how these expert-authored digital objects are collected, validated, and incorporated into the HRA and the major steps and timeline for releases, including who is responsible for each step.

Digital objects are added and revised on an ongoing basis, as the coverage of the Human Reference Atlas increases. Digital objects covered under the scope of this SOP include:

- 2D functional tissue unit illustrations
- 3D reference objects
- ASCT+B tables
- cell type annotation crosswalks
- millitomes
- OMAPs

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Every six months, a new release of the Human Reference Atlas (HRA) is published on the Human Reference Atlas Portal (<https://humanatlas.io>) (Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science Center 2025).

This document serves as a reference for those who have a role in the HRA release process and also serves as an overview of the process for contributors and users of the HRA. A basic familiarity with the HRA and the digital objects that comprise it is assumed (Börner et al. 2021; 2025). The SOP does not describe how various digital objects are authored, since the processes vary and are covered in other SOPs. See the HRA portal at <https://humanatlas.io/standard-operating-procedures> (Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science Center 2023) for a comprehensive list of SOPs.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **Digital Object Author** is the person who authors, and often revises, a new digital object. Typically, the Lead Organ Contact (LOC) serves as the lead author for digital objects related to their organ of focus. The LOC can invite other experts to author digital objects for inclusion in the HRA.

The **External Review Lead** sends digital objects to independent subject matter experts for review. External reviewer feedback is then shared with LOCs.

The **HRA Project Manager (PM)** is responsible for coordinating tasks, running weekly release meetings, and ensuring the release timeline is met. They ensure communication between the HRA Lead, Lead Organ Contacts, Validators, and the HRA Technical Lead is timely and productive.

The **HRA Integrator** is responsible for making sure that digital objects are submitted to the GitHub repository in preparation for integration into the HRA knowledge graph, and for ensuring that digital object metadata is complete and correct.

The **HRA Lead** is responsible for ensuring timely, high-quality, and on budget HRA releases.

Lead Organ Contacts (LOC) are domain experts for the organ of focus and work with subject matter experts to ensure digital objects are deemed accurate by a community of experts. LOCs might author all digital object types associated with their organ of focus, or invite others to author. LOCs present new and revised HRA digital objects, methods, and algorithms in the HRA working group prior to the HRA release for comments by the larger HRA community. LOCs approve final digital objects for their focus organ. For additional information on the LOC role see the SOP titled Serving as a Lead Organ Contact (Ruschman and Record 2025).

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Medical Illustrators provide 2D illustrations of functional tissue units, 3D reference objects, and icons representing organs, which are used on the HRA portal.

The **Ontology Validator** applies the validation pipeline (Caron et al. 2024) to check the accuracy of ontology relationships implicit in the ASCT+B tables against existing ontologies such as Uberon and Cell Ontology (CL).

The **HRA Technical Lead** handles the development, implementation, publication, and maintenance of HRA data, code, and knowledge graph. They also perform structural validation of all digital objects.

The **UX Designer** is responsible for compiling and publishing release notes that chronicle changes in each release. Release notes are shared on the Human Reference Atlas Portal.

The **Vasculature Validator** reviews ASCT+B tables to ensure that vasculature terms are consistent with those used for individual organs.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
Digital Object Author	various	
External Review Lead	Nancy Ruschman	infoccf@iu.edu
HRA Integrator	Hrishikesh Mulkutkar	infoccf@iu.edu
HRA Lead	Katy Börner	katy@iu.edu
HRA Project Manager (PM)	Nancy Ruschman	infoccf@iu.edu
HRA Technical Lead	Bruce W. Herr II	bherr@iu.edu
Lead Organ Contact (LOC)	various, one per organ	
Medical Illustrator	Rachel Bajema Heidi Schlehlein Ushma Patel	rbajema@iu.edu hschleh@iu.edu ushpatel@iu.edu
Ontology Validator	Aleix Puig Nicole Vasilevsky	aleix@ebi.ac.uk nvasilevsky@c-path.org
UX Designer	Elizabeth Maier	ecmaier@iu.edu
Vasculature Validator	Griffin Weber	griffin_weber@hms.harvard.edu

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Procedures

A six-month timeline is followed for each HRA release. The release process has five major milestones that function as critical junctures, see **Table 2**. Any digital objects that do not meet these milestones are automatically moved to the subsequent HRA release.

Table 2. HRA Release milestones and timeline.

HRA Release Timeline					
Phase	Milestone (indicates completion of the phase)	Success Criteria	Due (Spring)	Due (Fall)	Responsible Person
1 Identify and prioritize organs	A prioritized list of digital objects is compiled and LOCs for each organ in this release are confirmed	Prioritized list of organs, their new and revised DOs, and confirmed LOCs exists. HRAorg docs are shared with LOCs.	Feb 1	Aug 1	HRA Lead
2 Author and review DOs	DOs are shared with MC-IU	HRA digital objects have been submitted.	Apr 1	Oct 1	Lead Organ Contacts
3 Validate DOs	DOs are validated	All DOs have complete metadata and have been validated for ontology, vasculature connections, and formatting. Final revisions have been incorporated and LOC granted permission to publish.	May 1	Nov 1	HRA PM
4 Release HRA	A new version of the HRA is released	New and revised DOs have been integrated into the knowledge graph and HRA portal.	Jun 15	Dec 15	HRA Technical Lead
5 Integrate new release	Post-release tasks are complete	New documents are set up for the next release.	Jul 15	Jan 15	HRA Integrator

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Phase 1: Identify and prioritize organs

Developing a list of potential digital objects for the upcoming release

At the beginning of each release cycle, the HRA Lead compiles a prioritized list of organs and associated digital objects (see list of digital object types in **Table 3**) for the upcoming release. The list reflects the priorities of various consortia involved, the need to spatially register tissue data (Bueckle and Qaurooni Fard 2024), data availability, and funding.

- The list includes planned new and revised digital objects.
- A Lead Organ Contact has been confirmed for each organ.
- Needed single cell, 2D, and 3D data are available.
- Spatial data exists and needs to be spatially registered.

How Lead Organ Contacts (LOCs) are identified

- LOCs are identified by the HRA Lead. Contact with the LOC is initiated by the HRA Lead, usually via email.
- HRA PM sends an email to all committed LOCs, and asks them to provide an update on what they expect to deliver for the upcoming release.
- The LOC takes responsibility for verifying the accuracy of all digital objects (DOs) for their organ of focus.

Phase 2: Author and revise digital objects

HRAorg documents

Communication and approval of digital objects occur via HRAorg documents, which contain links to published and draft versions of all digital objects related to a particular organ.

- The HRA PM sets up HRAorg documents at the beginning of each release cycle for each organ that is expected to have at least one new or revised digital object in the upcoming release.
 - The HRAorg document template can be found as **Appendix A**.
 - The HRA PM prefills each section of the HRAorg document with links to existing digital objects, and to those in progress.
 - HRA PM ensures that all LOCs have edit access to the HRAorg document and they can view all digital objects that are linked from the document. LOCs may open up permissions to other organ experts as needed.
- HRA PM shares the HRAorg documents with each respective LOC.
- As each digital object is completed, the LOC notes that the digital object is ready for validation, and after validation they approve the finalized digital object for publication. If the LOC has questions or comments on a particular digital object, they reach out to the respective Digital Object Author.
- All digital objects need to be complete and ready for validation by April 1/Oct 1. After this

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

deadline, incomplete or unapproved digital objects are postponed to the next release.

Table 3. Sample signoff sheet for digital objects, found at the top of the HRAorg document.

Digital Object Type	Ready for Validation (initial and date)	Approved for Publication (initial and date)
2D functional tissue unit illustration		
3D reference object		
ASCT+B table		
cell type annotation crosswalk		
millitome		
OMAP		

Adding digital objects to GitHub

- The HRA Integrator collects all digital objects that have been approved for validation and adds them to the appropriate GitHub repository (<https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-kg/tree/main/digital-objects>).
- Complete versions of the digital objects are moved to the locations shown in **Table 4**. It is the responsibility of the Integrator to push the final version to the respective GitHub folders in the HRA-KG repository.

Table 4. Folder and GitHub locations for finalized digital objects (DOs)

DO Type	Folder for final DOs	Github
2D FTU illustrations	2D FTU Illustrations	https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-kg/tree/main/digital-objects/2d-ftu
3D reference objects	Heidi	https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-kg/tree/main/digital-objects/ref-organ
ASCT+B tables	Official_ASCT+B_Tables	https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-kg/tree/main/digital-objects/asct-b
cell type annotation crosswalks	Crosswalks	https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-kg/tree/main/digital-objects/cta

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

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millitomes	cns-iu/hra-amap: HRA-AMAP: Bidirectional Projections Between Human Atlas Systems for Data and Code Interoperability hubmapconsortium/hra-registrations: Manually curated HRA Dataset Graphs	https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-knowledge-graph/tree/main/digital-objects/millitome
OMAPs	Affinity Reagents	https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-knowledge-graph/tree/main/digital-objects/omap

- The Integrator updates metadata for each digital object in the appropriate metadata.yaml file.
 - For new digital objects, the Integrator uses a copy of an existing file or creates a new YAML file. Use the existing naming schema to name the file.
 - The Integrator transfers metadata for digital objects into a YAML file.
 - Example YAML file:
<https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-knowledge-graph/blob/main/digital-objects/asc-t-b/spinal-cord/v1.1/raw/metadata.yaml>
 - It is important to capture relevant publication references in the metadata.yml files and to update these regularly (e.g., replace bioarxiv with peer reviewed publication links, add links to new publications). Each reference should contain an ISBN (for books) or a DOI (e.g., <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2023.01.00>).
- For each new organ, the Medical Illustrator provides a new icon to the UX Designer. The UX Designer integrates it into the Figma style system and shares it with the development team via the HRA UI GitHub repository (<https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-ui>).
- The Integrator uploads the finalized digital objects and YAML files to the hra-knowledge-graph GitHub repository (<https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-knowledge-graph>).
- The Integrator initiates a pull request to incorporate the new raw data files and metadata into the knowledge graph main branch.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Phase 3: Validate digital objects

Validating digital objects

Digital objects undergo a series of validation checks before they are published. This ensures that digital objects have been reviewed for biological accuracy, have been incorporated into the relevant ontologies, use consistent terminology connecting them to the larger vasculature system, and are formatted appropriately for inclusion in the HRA knowledge graph. **Table 5** outlines which types of review and validation each kind of digital object undergoes.

- LOCs are expected to review and resolve comments during the validation period, i.e., the months of April and October. They are expected to continue to coordinate with additional experts as needed in order to respond to validation issues and reviewer comments that emerge during this validation phase.
- Digital objects that do not pass validation and cannot be revised in order to meet the timeline are moved to the next HRA release.

Table 5. Review and validation steps undergone by each digital object type.

Digital Object	internal review or SME	external review	ontology validation	vasculature validation	DO processor validation	DOI
2D functional tissue unit illustration	yes	no	no	yes	yes	yes
3D reference object	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
ASCT+B table	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
cell type annotation crosswalk	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes
millitome	yes	no	no	no	yes	yes
OMAP	yes	yes	no	no	yes	yes

Internal review or SME

- Digital objects described in this SOP are all reviewed internally prior to publication. Many are developed in partnership with subject matter experts (SMEs).

External review

- The HRA PM sends digital objects to independent subject matter experts for external review. Feedback from external reviewers is incorporated during Phase 2 of the release process, when digital objects are undergoing revision.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Ontology validation

- Ontology validation tools are run weekly against digital objects that have been submitted to the GitHub repository.
- This validation process ensures that digital objects have been incorporated into the relevant ontologies using consistent methods.

Vasculature validation

- Vasculature validation is done manually and ensures that all ASCT+B tables use vasculature terminology consistently.
- A detailed list of all changes made by the vasculature validator is shared via the HRAorg docs.
- These changes need to be reviewed and approved by the LOC prior to publication.

DO processor validation

- Beginning April 2/Oct 2, the HRA Technical Lead runs the build process to create a staging version of the knowledge graph. This DO processor checks for structural and formatting issues in digital objects. It is rerun multiple times leading up to each release as issues with integration are corrected.

OMAPS and AVRs

- To facilitate tissue mapping efforts within and beyond the HuBMAP community, OMAPs are designed for integration with the ASCT+B Reporter. OMAP development is handled by the Affinity Reagents Working Group, which is part of HuBMAP. See the existing SOP (McDonough et al. 2022) for more details.
- Each OMAP contains the OMAP Table and OMAP Description Document as well as 1) completed AVRs for each antibody included in the OMAP and 2) DOI for a representative dataset in a public repository such as the HuBMAP data portal or Zenodo.
- Antibody Validation Reports (AVRs, <https://avr.hubmapconsortium.org>) provide individual antibody validation information for the diverse antibody-based methods employed by HuBMAP members. OMAPs (<https://humanatlas.io/omap>) link to AVRs. For a description of how AVRs are constructed, see the relevant SOP (McDonough et al. 2022).

Phase 4: Release HRA

Digital object integration into the HRA Knowledge Graph

- Once all digital objects have been validated and approved for publication, the HRA Technical Lead merges all branches to the main development branch and runs the build process. This takes multiple (up to 14) hours to run.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

- The HRA Technical Lead registers digital object identifiers (DOI) for all digital objects, following the procedures outlined in the SOP titled Registering Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) (Quardokus 2022). It may take up to two weeks to receive DOIs. This step occurs after May 1/November 1, when all revisions are complete, and before June/December 15, when the release is published.
- The HRA Technical Lead updates the HRA portal statistics on the home page (<https://humanatlas.io>) and in the HRA Dashboard (<https://apps.humanatlas.io/dashboard>). These numbers are computed as part of the process of publishing the knowledge graph.
- Once the final build is complete, the HRA Technical Lead pushes the build to Amazon Web Service (AWS) and the knowledge graph is complete (Bueckle et al. 2025).

Digital object integration into user interfaces (EUI, RUI, Reporter, iFTU, Dashboard)

- Once the final build of the HRA knowledge graph is complete, updated digital objects are pushed to the HRA API and HRA user interfaces, including the ASCT+B Reporter.
- The HRA Technical Lead verifies all integrations are working and provides an HRA Portal staging site for review prior to the release.
- The HRA Technical Lead updates summary tables that appear on specific data pages of the HRA Portal, once the new version of the knowledge graph is available. These summary tables are different for each digital object type. The HRA Technical Lead has code that is run manually in order to update these tables.
- New releases are scheduled for June 15 and December 15. If the release date falls on a weekend, the release happens on the last business day before the official release date.

Drafting release notes

- For each new release, release notes are shared on the HRA portal, outlining what has changed. This section outlines the process for updating these release notes.
- The UX designer shares draft release notes via a Google document with the HRA Lead for review prior to publication.
- The UX Designer adds new release content to the Figma specification prototype, which is then pushed to the HRA Portal by the development team.

Phase 5: Integrate new release

Post-release procedures

- ASCT+B tables in the new release are frozen by the HRA Integrator
 - To lock a Google Doc so it can't be edited, use the Data icon in the toolbar and click on Protect sheets and ranges. Select sheet and click Set permissions. Provide edit access to Director, Associate Director and HRA Technical Lead.
- Copies of the new tables are made for the next release by the HRA Integrator.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

- ASCT +B Tables are located here:
https://drive.google.com/drive/u/2/folders/1g9cZs_qLYcXxv0dKUSq9VIQUVv1WS1jz.
 - Go to the respective organ.
 - Open the CSV of the latest version.
 - Click on File -> Make a copy.
 - Update the version number, delete any Data DOIs and date in the sheet and append “_DRAFT” to the title of the table.
 - Make sure to check the boxes Share it with the same people and Copy comments.
- The HRA Integrator adds draft ASCT+B tables to the ASCT+B reporter by adhering to a defined naming convention (e.g., screen_v1.6_draft) and updating the central listing sheet. The listing is refreshed by executing the script in the “Instructions for Reproducing” tab via Extensions > Apps Script in the associated Google Sheet. This script scans designated Drive folders, identifies draft tables based on their names, and populates the sheet with updated entries. The HRA API then references this listing to generate the sheet configuration, ensuring that the ASCT+B reporter displays the appropriate draft tables for preview and validation.
- Content edits for the portal are made as needed. There are inevitably a few small errors that are not caught at the time of release. These are added as GitHub issues for the development team to address. They are typically addressed in the week following a release.
- Datasets for new OMAPs are published by the HuBMAP Affinity Reagents Working Group in the Organ Mapping Antibody Panels community in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/omap/records>).
 - Add a link on the HRA portal (<https://humanatlas.io/omap>) to the OMAP dataset on Zenodo
- The Integrator uploads new and revised 2D FTUs and 3D reference objects to NIH portals (NIH 3D and BioArt) where they can be used by others. See the related SOPs (Mulikutkar, Kolahalama, et al. 2025; Mulikutkar, Kolachalama, et al. 2025) for details.
- The External Review Lead sends new and substantially revised digital objects out for external review soon after a new release launches. The HRA PM shares feedback with LOCs via HRAorg documents (see Append A at the end of this document) so that feedback can be incorporated during digital object revisions in Phase 2.
- The HRA data mirror sites are informed of the new release by the HRA Technical Lead. Mirror sites update mirrors to reflect new versions of the HRA as they become available, and within two weeks of a new release. See the Data Mirror SOP (Record and Herr 2025) for details.
- Post-release processes must be completed no later than July 15/January 15 so as not to impact the timeline for the next release.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

References and Resources

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Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Ruschman, Nancy, and Elizabeth Record. 2025. *Serving as a Lead Organ Contact*. July 16. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15977281>.

Glossary

3D reference object: Polygon mesh of 3D spatial objects (e.g., anatomical structures), their object node hierarchy, materials, and surface color and texture. They are created by medical illustrators with the involvement of subject matter experts following standard operating procedures.

ASCT+B tables: Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) Tables are authored by multiple experts across many consortia. Tables capture the partonomy of anatomical structures, cell types, and major biomarkers (e.g., gene, protein, lipid, or metabolic markers). Cellular identity is supported by scientific evidence and linked to ontologies.

antibody validation report (AVR): Document providing details on the characterization of individual antibodies for multiplexed antibody-based imaging assays. These details include target information (e.g., target name, UniProt accession number, and antibody information (e.g., RRID, host organism, vendor, catalog number, lot number). AVRs also provide details on controls used for antibody characterization (positive and negative tissues, cell lines, isotype controls, etc), exemplar imaging data, and information on other antibodies tested.

cell type annotation crosswalks: A collection of CSV files that link cell type labels from multiple datasets to Cell Ontology (CL) or Provisional Cell Ontology IDs so they can be connected to ASCT+B tables and other digital objects that are part of the Human Reference Atlas.

digital object (DO): Human Reference Atlas digital objects are the data components for generating the HRA knowledge graph. ASCT+B tables, 3D reference objects, and OMAPs are examples of HRA digital objects. Digital objects are often connected to specific ontologies via crosswalk tables.

digital object identifier (DOI): Centrally registered identifier composed of a string of numbers, letters and symbols used to uniquely identify an article or document with a permanent web address or Uniform Resource Locator (URL).

functional tissue unit (FTU): A functional tissue unit is the smallest tissue organization, i.e. a set of cells, that performs a unique physiologic function and is replicated multiple times in a whole organ. FTUs can be hierarchically nested.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

GitHub: An online service for version control and code-sharing.

HIVE: Integration, visualization and engagement teams which are part of the Human BioMolecular Atlas Program.

Human Reference Atlas (HRA): The Human Reference Atlas is a comprehensive, high-resolution, three-dimensional, multiscale atlas of all the cells in the healthy human body. The Human Reference Atlas provides standard terminologies and data structures for describing specimens, biological structures, and spatial positions linked to existing ontologies.

Mapping Component-Indiana University (MC-IU): The Indiana University team is one of two teams in the HuBMAP consortium tasked with building an atlas of tissue maps. These two teams are identified as mapping components, as opposed to components or teams that develop tools or provide infrastructure support.

ontology: A set of subject area concepts (here, anatomical structures, cell types and biomarkers), their properties and the relationships between them. Ontologies used in the Human Reference Atlas include Uberon and Cell Ontology (CL).

Organ Mapping Antibody Panel (OMAP): A comprehensive panel of curated antibodies that identifies the major anatomical structures and cell types in a specific organ. The selected antibodies are optimized for a tissue preservation method (i.e., fixed, frozen) and multiplexed imaging modality (e.g., CODEX, Cell DIVE) through published protocols (protocols.io) and AVR.

standard operating procedures (SOPs): SOPs are issued to specifically instruct team members in areas of responsibility, procedural steps, appropriate specifications and required records. SOPs outline procedures, which must be followed to support the reproducibility of scientific research. Procedures can take the form of a narrative, a flow chart, a process map, computer screen printouts or combination of all or any other suitable form, however must be written in appropriate, effective grammatical style (e.g., plain English).

subject matter expert (SME): An SME is a person with extensive knowledge about a given topic.

YAML file: YAML is a human-readable data serialization language typically used for writing configuration files.

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Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

efforts with expert input by the HRA Editorial Board and in close collaboration with experts from more than 18 other consortia. Data was provided by HuBMAP and other Tissue Mapping Centers. This research has been supported by the NIH Common Fund through the Office of Strategic Coordination/Office of the NIH Director under awards OT2OD033756 and OT2OD026671, by the Cellular Senescence Network (SenNet) Consortium through the Consortium Organization and Data Coordinating Center (CODCC) under award number U24CA268108, and by the NIDDK under awards U24DK135157 and U01DK133090. The work has also been supported by the Kidney Precision Medicine Project grant U2CDK114886, and the NIH National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID), Department of Health and Human Services under BCBB Support Services Contract HHSN316201300006W/HHSN27200002, as well as the American Dental Association Science and Research Institute and the Canadian Institute for Advanced Research's MacMillan Multiscale Human program. The content is solely the responsibility of the authors and does not necessarily represent the official views of the National Institutes of Health.

Appendix A. HRAorg Document Template

<insert release> HRA Org Document for <Organ>

Lead Organ Contact (LOC)

<insert name and email>

As lead organ expert, we would like to ask that you serve as the main point of contact for all Digital Objects (DOs). Please answer questions in a timely manner and work with the HRA team to maintain consistency, accuracy, and completeness of organ-specific content. See current SOP: Responsibilities of the Lead Organ Contact <insert link>.

For questions, please contact infoccf@iu.edu.

Official Approval

As LOC, initial each digital object when it is complete and ready for validation and again when the final version is approved for publication, see the [HRA Release Timeline](#).

Digital Object Type	Ready for Validation (initial and date)	Approved for Publication (initial and date)
ASCT+B tables		
2D functional tissue unit illustrations		
3D reference objects		
cell type annotation crosswalks		
OMAPs		
AVRs		
millitomes		
landmark organs		

ASCT+B Tables

Current ASCT+B tables: <https://humanatlas.io/asctb-tables>

New table that should be used to make changes for upcoming release: <insert link>

ASCT+B External Reviewer Comments

Table <insert version> was sent out to external experts and reviewer comments are provided below. Please consider these comments when making revisions. Please state which reviews you incorporated (e.g., all reviewers, reviewer #1 only, none). If reviews were not addressed, please provide your rationale here:

Reviewer #1

<insert comments>

Reviewer #2

<insert comments>

2D Functional Tissue Units (FTU)

Current FTU illustrations: <https://humanatlas.io/2d-ftu-illustrations>

Current crosswalk: [Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers \(ASCT+B\) Tables to 2D Functional Tissue Unit \(FTU\) Reference Object Library Crosswalk, Latest](#)

Please suggest revisions to existing and/or new FTU illustrations:

2D FTU External Review Comments

Table <insert version> was sent out to external experts and reviewer comments are provided below. Please consider these comments when making revisions. Please state which reviews you incorporated (e.g., all reviewers, reviewer #1 only, none). If reviews were not addressed, please provide your rationale here:

Reviewer #1

<insert comments>

Reviewer #2

<insert comments>

3D Reference Organ

Current FTU illustrations: [Human Reference Atlas Portal](#)

Current crosswalk: [Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers \(ASCT+B\) Tables to 3D Reference Object Library Crosswalk, Latest](#)

Please suggest revisions to existing and/or new 3D Reference Organs:

3D Reference Objects External Review Comments

Table <insert version> was sent out to external experts and reviewer comments are provided below. Please consider these comments when making revisions. Please state which reviews you incorporated (e.g., all reviewers, reviewer #1 only, none). If reviews were not addressed, please provide your rationale here:

Reviewer #1

<insert comments>

Reviewer #2

<insert comments>

OMAP (Organ Mapping Antibody Panels)

Current OMAPs: <https://humanatlas.io/omap>

<insert link to new or revised OMAPs>

Please review existing OMAPs and/or add new OMAPs and any questions or comments here:

AVR (Antibody Validation Report)

Current AVRs: <https://avr.hubmapconsortium.org> (not all are listed)

<insert link to new or revised AVR>

Please review the AVRs and/or add new AVRs add any questions or comments here:

Cell Type Annotation Crosswalks

Crosswalks: <https://humanatlas.io/cell-type-annotations>

Current Crosswalks: [Catalog for https://lod.humanatlas.io/ctann](https://lod.humanatlas.io/ctann)

Please review the crosswalks and add any questions or comments here:

Validation: Parsing Files for HRA KG Construction

Bruce W. Herr II is using the 200+ HRA DOs to compile the HRA KG, see details in (Bueckle et al. 2025). The following issues were encountered when reading your files:

<insert comments>

Validation: Existing Ontologies

EBI is running weekly validation reports, see (Caron et al. 2024) for details. Review the validation page for your ASCT+B table at

<https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-validation-tools/>. There are three links to review:

- General Report
- ASCT+B as Graph
- Report Changes

Please review the validation reports and add any questions or comments here:

Validation: Vasculature

Griffin Weber, Harvard Medical School has reviewed the HRA DOs and the following changes were made:

<insert comments>

Add any questions and comments you have here:

RUI Registrations

There exist <insert number> registered datasets for your organ.
<insert link to existing RUI Registrations in organ specific EUI>

Please review the RUI registrations and add any questions or comments here:

Millitomes

There exist <insert number> millitomes for your organ, see <https://humanatlas.io/millitome>.

Please review the millitome(s) and add any questions or comments here:

Landmark Organs

There exist <insert number> landmark organs for your organ, see [Catalog for https://lod.humanatlas.io/landmark](https://lod.humanatlas.io/landmark).

Please review these and add any questions or comments here:

Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs)

SOPs are found at <https://humanatlas.io/standard-operating-procedures>

References

- Bueckle, Andreas, Bruce W. Herr, Josef Hardi, Ellen M. Quardokus, Mark A. Musen, and Katy Börner. 2025. "Construction, Deployment, and Usage of the Human Reference Atlas Knowledge Graph." *Scientific Data* 12 (1): 1100. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-05183-6>.
- Caron, Anita Reane, Aleix Puig-Barbe, Ellen M. Quardokus, et al. 2024. "A General Strategy for Generating Expert-Guided, Simplified Views of Ontologies." Preprint, bioRxiv, December 18. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.12.13.628309>.